

A Comparative Study on the Kinetics of Oxidation of some Organic Sulphides by Quinolium Chlorochromate and Hexacyanoferrate(III)

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The mechanism of oxidation of organic sulphides depends largely on the nature of the oxidant rather than the conditions of experiment. In this communication, the rates of oxidation of dialkyl and alkyl phenyl sulphides by quinolium chlorochromate (QCC) and potassium hexacyanoferrate(III) are compared

Results and Discussion

The results of the study are presented in Tables 1-6. The results of kinetic investigation are summarised in Table 7. Consistent with the observed rate laws the mechanisms proposed for the two oxidants are presented in Scheme 1. Oxygen trans-

TABLE 1-RATE DATA OF THE OXIDATION OF SULPHIDES (MeSR, WHERE R = Et, Ph) WITH QCC AND $K_3Fe(CN)_6$ AT 308 ± 0.2 K

Sl no	[Sulphide] $\times 10^3 M$	[QCC] $\times 10^4 M$	[$K_3Fe(CN)_6$] $\times 10^3 M$	[HClO ₄] $\times 10^2 M$	% AcOH-H ₂ O v/v	$k_{obs} (\times 10^3 s^{-1})$		n
						MeSEt	MeSPh	
1	5.0-15.0	5.0	-	4.8	50	3.53-12.77	-	6
2	5.0-15.0	5.0	-	12.0	50	-	2.63-7.92	6
3	5.0	2.5-7.5	-	4.8	50	3.89-3.51	-	6
4	5.0	5.0	-	2.4-7.2	50	1.73-5.40	-	6
5	5.0	5.0	-	4.8	30-70	0.90-16.32	-	9
6	13.2-52.7	-	1.0	6.0	70	0.71-3.63	-	7
7	10.0-50.0	-	1.0	13.0	70	-	0.35-2.02	5
8	26.4	-	0.5-2.5	6.0	70	1.82-0.94	-	5
9	26.4	-	1.0	40-80	70	0.49-8.46	-	9
10	26.4	-	1.0	6.0	60-75	0.34-6.68	-	4

TABLE 2-RATE DATA FOR A TYPICAL SYSTEM

[EtSMe] = $5.0 \times 10^{-3} M$, [QCC] = $5.0 \times 10^{-4} M$, [HClO₄] = $4.8 \times 10^{-4} M$, AcOH-H₂O 50%(v/v), Temp = 35°

Time (s)	30	45	60	75	90	120	150	180	210	240	270	300	330	360	390
Absorbance	0.538	0.507	0.482	0.458	0.433	0.386	0.350	0.315	0.283	0.255	0.230	0.207	0.186	0.167	0.150

$k = 3.53 \times 10^{-3} s^{-1}$

TABLE 3-EFFECT OF SOLVENT COMPOSITION ON THE OXIDATION RATE

% AcOH	30	35	40	45	50	55	60	65	70	75
γ	2.56	2.45	2.31	2.15	1.96	1.75	1.52	1.27	0.99	0.68
QCC	17.92	26.70	36.71	52.70	70.57	108.60	159.00	235.00	326.36	-
$k_2 (\times 10^2 M^{-1} s^{-1})$										
$K_3Fe(CN)_6$	-	-	-	-	-	-	1.31	2.66	6.45	25.36

TABLE 4—RELATIVE RATES OF OXIDATION AND ORDER OF REACTIVITY OF DIALKYL SULPHIDES

Sulphide	Relative rates of oxidation		
	QCC	K ₃ Fe(CN) ₆	PDC
Me ₂ S	100	100	100
EtSMe	89	93	—
Et ₂ S	83	82	—
Pr ₂ S	74	60	67
Bu ₂ S	64	55	64
iso-Pr ₂ S	29	11	25

The order of reactivity is Me₂S > EtSMe > Pr₂S > Bu₂S > iso-Pr₂S.

TABLE 5—RELATIVE RATES OF OXIDATION AND ORDER OF REACTIVITY OF ALKYL, PHENYL SULPHIDES

Sulphide	Relative rates of oxidation					
	QCC	K ₃ Fe(CN) ₆	P ₂ O ₈ ⁴⁻	S ₂ O ₈ ²⁻	Cr ⁶⁺	PIA
PhSMe	100	100	100	100	100	100
PhSEt	88	71	66	41	80	88
PhSPr	77	62	56	31	76	80
PhSiso-Pr	54	38	32	15	47	72
PhSt-Bu	28	9	6	1.8	11	42

The order of reactivity is PhSMe > PhSEt > PhSPr > PhS iso-Pr > PhSt-Bu.

TABLE 6—BIMOLECULAR RATE CONSTANTS AND ACTIVATION PARAMETERS FOR THE OXIDATION OF ORGANIC SULPHIDES WITH QCC AND K₃Fe(CN)₆

Sulphide	QCC						K ₃ Fe(CN) ₆						
	<i>k</i> ₂ (× 10 ² M ⁻¹ s ⁻¹)				Δ <i>H</i> [#]	-Δ <i>S</i> [#]	<i>k</i> ₂ × 10 ³ M ⁻¹ s ⁻¹					Δ <i>H</i> [#]	Δ <i>S</i> [#]
	25 ^o	30 ^o	35 ^o	40 ^o			25 ^o	30 ^o	35 ^o	40 ^o	45 ^o		
Me ₂ S	59.26	70.50	79.54	—	19.98	182.27	36.64	51.82	69.00	96.94	—	47.21	114.08
EtSMe	—	60.27	70.57	80.92	20.72	180.98	31.79	48.23	64.52	80.85	97.23	40.96	135.68
Et ₂ S	—	57.47	65.74	78.04	21.57	178.66	30.05	42.64	56.26	74.90	95.47	42.35	131.78
Pr ₂ S	—	48.26	58.54	68.13	24.68	169.74	22.91	31.99	41.28	56.03	74.27	43.38	130.81
Bu ₂ S	—	41.34	50.64	59.96	26.78	164.09	21.40	29.24	37.84	55.03	71.97	45.64	123.95
iso-Pr ₂ S	—	18.56	22.97	27.37	28.11	166.38	—	5.31	7.85	10.39	12.96	41.69	150.63
PhSMe	—	42.84	52.63	65.14	30.51	151.54	—	25.46	36.02	47.20	63.59	45.80	124.43
PhSEt	—	35.56	45.69	55.82	33.05	144.63	—	19.43	25.56	33.71	47.66	44.99	129.63
PhSPr	—	31.82	41.08	51.62	35.64	137.04	—	17.39	22.33	32.11	43.23	47.05	123.82
PhSiso-Pr	—	21.86	29.16	38.88	42.85	116.40	—	9.44	13.68	19.88	24.29	48.98	122.07
PhSt-Bu	—	8.68	14.98	20.69	66.07	47.16	—	—	3.24	4.92	6.96	59.78	99.14

TABLE 7—SALIENT FEATURES OF KINETIC INVESTIGATION

Oxidant : QCC or K₃Fe(CN)₆, Reductant : organic sulphides, Temp. 308 K

Various effects	Oxidant		Inference
	QCC	K ₃ Fe(CN) ₆	
Plot of log <i>k</i> _{obs} vs log[sulphide]	←	→	First order w.r.t substrate
Plot of log(absorbance) vs time at higher concentration of sulphides	←	→	First order w.r.t.oxidant
Effect of [H ⁺]	First order	Fourth order	Protonated oxidant is reactive species
Effect of Mn ²⁺ (2.5×10 ⁻³ to 10.0×10 ⁻³ M)	Appreciable decrease in rate (2.07×10 ⁻³ to 1.30×10 ⁻³ s ⁻¹)	—	Two-electron change in rate determining step ^a
Effect of K ₄ Fe(CN) ₆ (1.0×10 ⁻³ to 4.0×10 ⁻³ M)	—	Decrease in rate (9.61×10 ⁻⁴ to 3.16×10 ⁻⁴ s ⁻¹)	One of the products is the protonated form of hexacyanoferrate(III)
Effect of acrylonitrile (0.2 M)	—	Decrease in rate (1.7×10 ⁻³ s ⁻¹ to 1.4×10 ⁻³ s ⁻¹)	Free radical formation in rate-determining step
Effect of NaClO ₄ (0.05 M)	←	→	—
Increase in dielectric constant of the medium	←	→	—
Grunwald-Winstein equation ^b log <i>k</i> ₂ = log <i>k</i> ₀ + <i>mY</i>	Linear <i>r</i> = 0.993, <i>s</i> = 0.05 <i>m</i> = -0.79, log <i>k</i> ₀ = 1.37 (± 0.036) (± 0.070)	Linear <i>r</i> = 0.994, <i>s</i> = 0.071 <i>m</i> = -1.52, log <i>k</i> ₀ = 0.39 (± 0.113) (± 0.131)	S _N 2 type of transition state
Product analysis	IR	IR	Sulphoxide
Stoichiometry	1 : 1	1 : 2	—
Rate law	[QCC] [sulphide] [H ⁺]	[Fe(CN) ₆ ³⁻] [sulphide] [H ⁺] ⁴	—

^aValues from Ref. 1, ^bValues from Ref. 2.

fer from QCC is in agreement with the earlier observations

is sensitive to steric congestion at the reaction centre rather than the electronic effects

Experimental

QCC was prepared by the literature method⁵ Acetic acid was refluxed over chromic oxide for 6 h and then fractionated The experiment was carried out by mixing the sulphide and the oxidant solutions under pseudo-first order conditions (always sulphide in excess) in requisite quantity of aqueous acetic acid The rates were followed spectrophotometrically at 360 and 418 nm in oxidations with QCC and $K_3Fe(CN)_6$ respectively

If the contribution of the +I effect of the alkyl groups predominates over the steric effect exerted by the increasing bulkiness of the alkyl groups, one would expect a reverse order in the rate Further, there is a satisfactory correlation between $\log(k_2/k_2(\text{Me}))$ values with Taft's steric substituent constants⁴, E_s (slope = 0.35, $r = 0.980$, $s = 0.05$ for QCC oxidation, and slope = 0.32, $r = 0.987$, $s = 0.03$ for $K_3Fe(CN)_6$ oxidation) All these facts clearly indicate that the reaction

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